

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF BLENDED LEARNING IN IMPROVING ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILL: A STUDY ON NON-ENGLISH MAJOR FRESHMEN AT HO CHI MINH CITY UNIVERSITY OF FOOD INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

It is obviously undeniable that being able to speak English confidently and correctly has been a big challenge of almost all HUFU freshmen. Thus, to make the students interested and confident to express their ideas in English, the writer applied blended learning method. The main focus of this paper is to observe the implementation of blended learning in teaching English speaking. The subject of this quantitative research is the first-year students in two classes. The data were collected by interviewing the speaking teacher, observing the classroom activities and giving the questionnaire to the students. The results of the study indicated that the application of blended learning in teaching English speaking at university was able to motivate the students to speak confidently. In short, this research showed that the use of blended learning in teaching English speaking not only provided teachers with pedagogically effective ways in the teaching process but also created the motivation for the students to speak English effectively.

Key words: Blended learning, English speaking, English speaking teaching and learning, motivation

1 INTRODUCTION

The fast development of technology has brought a lot of benefits for education. This has created a tremendous change, particularly improving teaching and learning inputs, processes and outcomes thanks to developing possible solutions. Information technology in general, or social networks in particular, helps both teachers and learners of second languages apply new teaching and learning practices. Elliot (2009) indicates that the use of information and communication technology (ICT) has shifted teachers from traditional teaching method towards teaching using the advancement of Internet. The ICT tools provide better teaching and learning experiences, enhancing using the latest technologies in teaching and learning (Kose, 2010). As a result, teachers are starting to apply blended learning in their instructing by combining both face-to-face and online learning. There are a variety of recent studies proving that adopting blended learning has brought certain effects in improving learning performance.

The oral communication skill is one of the essential competencies for the students at HUFU, for they are required to pass the exam for the B1 certificate according to the Vietnamese 6-level foreign language frame. Teachers of English at HUFU have recently applied the use of technologies for enhancing the quality of English learning and teaching, particularly asking students to work online at home besides in-class attendance. This was an important step, helping develop and embed a blended learning strategy in the best of face-to-face learning experiences. The teacher has applied the blended approach in teaching speaking to HUFU freshmen and also got some experience. In this article, the researcher desired to investigate why English teachers ought to apply blended learning, to identify the tools used in blended learning, and to indicate how blended learning motivated students in improving English speaking.

To sum up, the findings of the research may hopefully help improve teaching and learning English speaking in the future. Therefore, the above issues need to be solved to put forward some suggestions in planning and implementing blended learning.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Blended learning

The term *blended learning* was first known around 2000 and associated with simply supplementing traditional classroom learning with self-study e-learning activities. Blended learning has been defined in different ways by many researchers. However, almost all definitions shared the core meaning of blended learning which is mixing two categories: face-to-face teaching and online education.

Bath & Bourke (2010:1) cite the definition of blended learning as follow:

Blended learning is realised in teaching and learning environments where there is an effective integration of different modes of delivery, models of teaching and styles of learning as a result of adopting a strategic and systematic approach to the use of technology combined with the best features of face to face interaction (Krause, 2007).

In addition, (Klapwijk, 2008:4) believes that blended learning is “a mixture of multimedia technology, CD ROM videos, virtual classrooms, voicemail, email and conference calls, online text animation and video streaming and that all these are combined with traditional forms of classroom training and one-to-one coaching”. Then Klapwijk (2008) also argues that blended learning components might consist of computer and non-computer based educational tools (as shown in Table 1).

Table 1: Computer and Non-Computer Based Educational Components (Klapwijk, 2008:43)

Non-Computer Educational Components	Computer-Based Educational Components
- Classroom based audio-tape resources (language laboratories).	- Multimedia technology.
- Auditorium multimedia visual resources (movies, projectors, slideshows, VCRs).	- CD ROM video streaming.
- Home learning resources (video, recording, audio recording).	- Virtual classrooms.
- Black board and white board resources.	- Printing whiteboards and online whiteboards.
- Demonstration resources including: museum exhibits, laboratory experiments, live theatre, historic reenactment, hands-on workshops, role-playing, etc.	- Online text animation and video streaming (the Web)
- Nontechnical educational resources such as, examination, quizzes, invigilation and test-grading.	- Mobile learning or (PDAs, handle computers).
- Classroom discussion, group discussions and written notes.	- Voicemail, email, SMS and conference calls.

By the same idea, Bath & Bourke (2010:1) emphasizes that blended learning is about effectively integrating Information and Communication Technologies into course design to enhance teaching and learning experiences for students and teachers by enabling them to engage in ways that would not normally be available or effective in their usual environment, whether it is primarily face to face or distance mode. In many cases the act of “blending” achieves better student experiences and outcomes, and more efficient teaching and course management practices. It can involve a mix of delivery modes, teaching approaches and learning styles.

According to Saliba, Rankine & Cortez (2013:4), blended learning refers to a strategic and systematic approach to combining times and modes of learning, integrating the best aspects of face-to-face and online interactions for each discipline, using appropriate ICTs. A blend might include:

face-to-face and online learning activities and formats;

traditional timetabled classes with different modes, such as weekend, intensive, external, trimester;

well established technologies such as lecture capture, and/or with social media and emerging technologies;

simulations, group activities, site-based learning, practicals.

Similarly, a blended learning model might include instructor-delivered content, e-learning, webinars, conference calls, live or online sessions with instructors, and other media and events, for example, Facebook, e-mail, chat rooms, blogs, podcasting, Twitter, YouTube, Skype and web boards. Pankin et al. at MIT (2012:1) define blended as:

Structure opportunities to learn, which use more than one learning or training method, inside or outside the classroom.

The definition includes different learning or instructional methods (lecture, discussion, guided practice, reading, games, case study, simulation), different delivery methods (live classroom or computer mediated) and different scheduling (synchronous or asynchronous).

Based on the definitions listed above, blended learning has many benefits that no one can deny. As a matter of fact, blended learning is an innovative teaching approach, combining different methods of learning supported by flexible and diverse resources that offer new approaches in teaching language skills and enhancing competences. The researchers have been clarified the benefits of blended learning such as increasing access and flexibility for learners, increasing level of active learning, and achieving better student experiences and outcomes. For teachers, blended learning can improve teaching and class management practices.

Bath & Bourke (2010) identify the following strengths of blended learning technologies:

Broaden the spaces and opportunities available for learning;

Support course management activities (e.g., communication, assessment submission, marking and feedback);

Support the provision of information and resources to students;

Engage and motivate students through interactivity and collaboration.

In other words, “blended learning is about finding better ways of supporting students in achieving the learning objectives and providing them with the best possible learning and teaching experiences, as well as supporting teachers in their role (including the management and administration of courses). Of course, the integration of blended learning in courses will naturally vary according to such factors as: discipline, year level, student characteristics and needs, course or program learning objectives, as well as the academic’s approach to teaching, and confidence and experience in using technology” (Bath & Bourke , 2010:1).

To make it clear, Bath & Bourke (2010) mention that adapting a blended learning approach can be used to support face-to-face teaching, large group and small group learning, self-directed learning, communication between the teacher and individual students or groups of students, as well as between students themselves. Teachers themselves can “blend” *time* (e.g., face-to-face vs. recorded lectures), *place* (small group tutorial on-campus vs. online discussion forum; traditional field trip vs. ‘virtual’ field trip using web sites and online chat with industry personnel), *people* (podcast of guest lecturers, or virtual classroom to include both on-campus and off-campus students), *resources* and *activities* (textbook vs. online readings; in-class vs. online quiz). This can be shown as in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1: Possibilities for blended learning (Bath & Bourke, 2010:4)

2.2 Teaching and learning English speaking skill

Speaking is an essential ability of second language (EFL/ESL) learning and teaching, and the mastery of English speaking skill is a priority for EFL students. Students often measure their success in language learning as well as the effectiveness of their English course on the basis of how much they feel they have improved in their spoken language proficiency; as a result, oral skills have hardly been ignored in English as a foreign or second language courses at present.

Brown (1994) points out that the role of learners in developing speaking skill comprises: (1) intensive – it goes one step beyond imitative to include any speaking performance designed to practice some phonological or grammatical aspects of language; (2) responsive – it include short replies to teacher-or-student-initiated questions or comments; (3) transactional – it is performed for the aims of conveying or exchanging specific information; (4) interpersonal – it helps to

maintain social relationships than for the transmission of information, and these dialogues are little difficult for learners due to some factors like a colloquial language, emotionally charged language, slang, and sarcasm; and (5) extensive – it is more formal and deliverative, and it can be planned. Thereafter, Brown (2007) determines two types of spoken language: interpersonal and transactional. The former is about giving comment for a given topic and is characterized by continuously shifting topics and a lot of agreement on them. The latter occurs when the purpose of the speaker is to convey information.

Moreover, according to Brown (2007), the difficulties of speaking are determined by eight factors, including (1) clustering in which speech is phrasal, not word by word; (2) redundancy, or the over-use of words; (3) reduced form, or the use of contractions, elisions, and reduced vowels; (4) performance variables related to hesitations, pauses, backtracking and corrections; (5) colloquial language in which learners relate words with idioms and phrases; (6) rate of delivery to help learners achieve an acceptable speed along with other attributes of fluency; (7) stress, rhythm, and intonation used to convey meaning; and (8) interaction, or the creativity of conversational negotiation. Based on these determined factors, teachers are supposed to plan lessons carefully.

As a result, Brown (2007) discusses principles for teaching speaking skill, consisting of focusing on fluency and accuracy, equipping motivating techniques, enhancing the use of authentic language in meaningful contexts, providing feedback and correction, linking speaking and listening, offering opportunities for oral communication, and encouraging the development of speaking strategies. In addition, Nunan (2003) shows the goals of teaching speaking:

Produce the English speech sounds and sound patterns;

Use word and sentence stress, intonation patterns and the rhythm of the second language;

Select appropriate words and sentences according to the proper social setting audience, situation and subject matter;

Organize their thoughts in a meaningful and logical sequence;

Use language as a means of expressing values and judgments;

Use the language quickly and confidently with few unnatural pauses, which is called as fluency.

2.3 Blended learning in teaching and learning speaking skill

Bahadorfar & Omidvar (2014) argue that technology can stimulate the playfulness of learners and involve them in a diverse range of communicative situations. Technology helps students engage in self-directed actions, self-paced interactions, privacy, and a safe environment in which errors get corrected and specific feedback is given. Researchers emphasized when links are provided to include explanations, additional support, and reference, the value of technology in language learning and teaching is further augmented.

Parveen (2016) lists modern technologies as:

Communication lab

Video conferencing

Video Library

CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning)

Speech recognition software

Programmes through educational satellites

Blogging

Internet

TELL (Technology Enhanced Language Learning)

Pod casting

Quick Link Pen

Quicktionary

The point is that it is the time to incorporate modern technologies to promote the level of English teaching. Specifically, the practice of Internet has brought dramatic change in the field of enhancing English learning. The students can browse the different applications and online teaching aids like Skype, Viber, Facebook, Zalo, Twitter, etc., connect themselves with friends, other students, lecturers and foreign teachers, and improve their oral competence and intercultural awareness, motivation and raise the level of interaction. One more example is that thanks to blogging, the teachers can post the instruction to the students and allow their students to post comments and queries, creating a chance to keep in touch and practice language skills continuously. Another useful resource is pod casting which helps to upload and download the audio files in English. The teachers can use them as useful audio material for classroom activities like discussions, or include pronunciation for learning different accents to enhance speaking skills; the students can exploit these materials inside and outside the classrooms in the form of entertainment as the part of their learning (Parveen, 2016).

To sum up, ICTs offer possibilities to improve communication skills, self-expression, and comprehension. Besides, social utilities provide many communicative variances for online community development. As a result, blended approach might be adapted in the environment of teaching and learning English speaking skill.

3 METHODOLOGY

The participants involved in this study were 100 non-English major freshmen of different fields of study including engineering, financing and banking, business administration and accounting. These students were taking part in the English 2 course after they finished the English 1 course. They need to learn English due to the foreign language requirements set by the University, and

for the demand of English language in their future jobs. They were required to participate in classes for a duration of 45 forty-five-minute periods with both Vietnamese and foreign lecturers and to self-study online with the support of the website <http://www.cengageasia.com/vietnamlife/training> and the contact with the immediate instructor through e-mails, messengers, facebook, viber, zalo, etc.

Quantitative research methodology was utilized to carry out this study. The researcher employed a survey methodology to collect and analyze the data. First, the class observation was carried out throughout the course by the Vietnamese instructor. Then questionnaires were handed out in class at the end of the course. Finally, an interview was given to the immediate teacher including open-ended questions to gain comments on the teacher’s experience and evaluation of the whole process. The quantitative data were prepared for analysis using the Excel software, and the comments and open ended questions were analyzed as well.

4 FINDINGS

The questionnaires were delivered to the students as soon as the course was completed. The questionnaires were aimed to get the students’ response to applying blended learning in their learning (as shown in Table 2).

Table 2: Students’ Response to Blended Learning

No.	Question	Strongly Agree %	Agree %	No opinion %	Disagree %	Strongly disagree %
1	Blended learning brings a lot of benefits in English speaking learning.	26	40	18	11	5
2	Blended learning is more convenient and flexible than traditional learning method.	10	38	12	35	5
3	Blended learning helps increase my motivation for learning English.	15	39	16	20	10
4	Blended learning makes me more confident in practice speaking English.	20	25	28	25	2
5	I can study a lot outside classrooms from my teacher and classmates thanks to blended	45	38	4	13	0

No.	Question	Strongly Agree %	Agree %	No opinion %	Disagree %	Strongly disagree %
	learning.					
6	I can organize my time and do my online homework and assignments on time.	54	28	3	10	5
7	The learning material in blended learning is explained clearly.	39	18	0	33	10
8	Blended learning is boring.	38	14	0	16	32
9	Blended learning in speaking skill needs more time and effort.	66	22	6	6	0
10	Loading the online-workbook is very slow.	11	6	0	59	24
11	The Internet service often stops.	35	38	4	20	3
12	I don't have any electronic devices to learn online.	7	11	0	56	26
13	I don't have the required skills to make use of Internet.	5	8	15	55	17
14	The evaluation in online learning is fair and correct.	15	8	8	57	12
15	It is difficult to interact with the lecturer.	27	15	5	30	23

As shown in Table 2, most students agreed that they achieved a lot of benefits from blended learning, and really enhanced their motivation to learn English. Moreover, blended learning experience was more convenient and flexible than traditional learning. Although only 45% of the students felt more confident in practice speaking English, the majority pointed out that they could receive a lot of knowledge outside classrooms thanks to blended learning, with more than 80%. Furthermore, according to 82% of the students, the time organization for online homework and assignments was managed effectively, and more than half of the students agreed that the learning material in blended learning was instructed clearly.

However, 52% felt bored with blended learning, whereas 48% disagreed. Most of the students agreed that blended learning needed more time and effort, especially in speaking skill. Although most students pointed out that loading the online-workbook was not slow, they affirmed the Internet interruption often happened.

Fortunately, almost all students showed that they equipped themselves with electronic devices and the necessary skills to make use of Internet in online learning. Apart from this, nearly 70% affirmed that the evaluation in online learning was fair and correct. Finally, the interaction with the lecturer during the blended process was considered to be difficult by less than half of the students.

Apart from the findings of the questionnaires, the data were collected from the class observation and the interview with the in-charge teacher. On one hand, the findings showed that blended learning helped solve the problem of in-class time constraint. In addition, blended learning encouraged the students to be confident, independent and responsible in their learning. The students could improve their language skills through intensive online material including quizzes, assignments, and homework. In fact, blended learning was very beneficial for the students in terms of learning vocabulary, pronunciation and grammar, which enhanced them to speak out confidently. Besides, blended learning gave self-assessment and improved both the students' and teachers' technology skills. The observation also indicated that the students liked to be involved in blended learning because they were not required to spend a lot of time in class, and that blended learning was really convenient.

On the other hand, the access to the Internet was sometimes not available at school and at students' homes, and not all students had computers, laptops or smart phones that enabled them to take part in online learning. Some weak students relied on other students in completing the online tasks. Occasionally, blended learning caused boredom and distraction for the students.

5 DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the obtained findings, it was revealed that blending learning had a positive and significant effect on the English speaking ability among HUFU EFL freshmen. The results show that the students were excited with the blended learning. Almost all students agreed that the blended learning was convenient, flexible, and beneficial. Moreover, they showed that this approach helped them increase the autonomy, independence, motivation and time management.

However, implementing the blended learning faced some difficulties and should be solved in some ways. In other words, it is important to know the factors that affect the successful of ICT in teaching and learning English speaking skill. When students are introduced a course blended with ICT, there are some factors that affect their decision and performance concerning how and when they can use it.

First, the Internet service was often slow or unavailable; hence, it is necessary to apply the designed multimedia program and other materials offline. The university should equip the learning environment with all that is needed for the new learning procedure; it is required to provide sufficient computer labs, Wifi, technicians, and all necessity. Next, the speaking materials were not flexible enough; thus, the lecturer should provide the students with extra materials for speaking training.

Evaluation is another important factor that affects the successful implementation of blended learning. The students should be provided by immediate evaluation and support that will motivate them to continue learning. The teacher should have the ability to assess and evaluate what students do online. To do that, the teacher should have full control and supervision on the online tasks, and set realistic goals for the blended learning students, and make the transition gradual, but not a sudden leap.

Moreover, the problem is learner computer anxiety and students' technology level, and that could be addressed by giving clear and immediate support from both the teacher and the foreign language center staff. To put simply, the students were reluctant to participate and cooperate with both the teacher and classmates through the website or social networks because they were not used to such approach in learning before. To solve this problem, the teacher should encourage the students to get accustomed to a new learning habit due to its benefits, follow the students' participation on the website every day, and remind them by sending inquiries through e-mails, and so on.

Another important point is that the teacher should pay attention to students' learning styles because learning styles greatly impact the instructional environments due to their potential in fostering learning. The learning style instructors use can attract students continue learning. Individual differences and personal characteristics should be taken into consideration when implementing technology in language learning. The educational technology suits shy students who avoid face-to-face contact with other students and prefer to communicate with others electronically.

Finally, Bath & Bourke (2010:7) point out that good preparation and decision-making is essential not only for efficient use of instructors' time in the construction and maintenance of the resources, but also for the creation of quality experiences for the students. Generally, blended learning design process goes throughout five stages:

Planning for integrating blended learning into the course.

Designing and developing the blended learning elements.

Implementing the blended design.

Reviewing (evaluating) the effectiveness of the blended learning design.

Planning for the next presentation of the course that requires improving the blended learning experience for both staff and students.

Figure 2: The Blended Learning Design Process (Bath & Bourke, 2010:7)

To sum up, the implementation of blended learning in speaking class for non-English major freshman at HUFU not only gained benefits but also faced some difficulties; therefore, there should be a careful design process to enhance the good points and to overcome challenges in the blended learning.

6 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the communication skill in oral form is one of the crucial competencies to students to finish the university program; also, this capability will greatly support them in their future jobs. Various attempts were made by many education institutions all over the world to equip the graduates with good communication skill. On the other hand, in Viet Nam, the present study comes into conclusion that blended learning is an effective approach toward teaching the English communicative skills. This study was designed to conform to the requirements set forth by the English teaching syllabus for English non-major students at HUFU. Blended EFL strategies are used where the students can engage in self-study activities, or online-homework in particular. Apart from this, they can also be included into a traditional classroom setting to assist EFL instruction and learning as the existing English communication course does not function properly in achieving the goals of English teaching at HUFU. Also, it doesn't develop the learners' speaking because of the traditional methods such as imitating and retelling; the learners lose interest and get bored easily with doing these activities and pay less attention to practicing their speaking. In fact, the learning motivation has been enhanced. However, having in mind that the aim of blended learning is to equip the students to use virtual devices to learn better, this research inspires the curriculum developers to make changes in the materials, developing more especial online materials or websites to influence the learning and teaching quality to be innovative in the performance on learning. Similarly, there is a must to develop and implement new methods and activities in the speaking classes. As a result, using an online course via blended learning approach could play a very important role to improve students' speaking.

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